

Effect of Temperature on the Structural, Morphological and Optical Properties of Hydrothermally Synthesised Titanium Dioxide

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ABSTRACT:

Three samples of titanium dioxide nanoparticles were prepared by hydrothermal treatment at three different temperatures (140°C, 180°C, 220°C) using a strong acid (HNO₃). The precursors were heated for 8 hours to form the TiO₂ structure, and then thin films were formed on a glass base using a spin coater, then structural properties were studied. The lattice constants were equal to $a = b = 3784 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9515 \text{ \AA}$ for all samples and the crystal structure is tetragonal. FESEM imaging showed that the surface was smooth with few pores and the grain size was about 117.298 ~ 148.355 nm for sample1 (prepared at 140°C), 85 ~ 124.981 nm for sample2 prepared at 180°C and 56.545 ~ 89.056 nm for sample3 prepared at 220°C. Uv-v characterisation has shown that the first structure has a higher transmittance than the other two structures for visible light beam, but in general all samples have low absorbance for all spectral regions. The band gap energy was increased as the heating temperature increased where it was around 2.62 eV for sample1 and 2.82 eV for structure2 also sample3 has a wider band gap around 2.86eV.

Keywords: Hydrothermal treatment, Transmittance, Absorbance, Autoclave.

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INTRODUCTION

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles have been widely studied due to their diverse applications: Optics, solar energy coatings, electronics, including electric batteries, optical receptors, catalysts in chemical reactions, antimicrobial compounds, optical coating materials, photonic devices, gas sensors, cosmetics, and others [1]. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is a chemically stable substance with favourable semiconductor properties. It has three different crystal structures: anatase, rutile and brookite [2]. The rutile structure is the most chemically stable of the other forms; however, at the nanoscale, anatase exhibits greater stability than the other two phases due to the higher surface energy required for rutile growth. Anatase is widely recognised for its superior solar electrical conversion efficiency (SECE) and photocatalytic activity compared to rutile, due to its distinctive electronic structures, including a larger band gap and higher electron mobility [4]. The photocatalytic performance is influenced by several parameters, including the crystallisation process, composition, grain surface properties, crystal size and shape (5). The rutile phase has superior photocatalytic activity for

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optoelectronic applications, depending on various modifications, and has a higher refractive index that allows light scattering within the crystal structure planes (6). There are numerous methods available to create different morphologies of oxide or dioxide nanostructures, including sol-gel, precipitation, anodisation and hydrothermal treatments [7]. Hydrothermal is the preferred feasible method, especially in this study, because it provides the best control of morphological and crystallographic information properties by simply changing the preparation conditions such as duration, solvent type, temperature and pressure. Furthermore, different types of phases and morphological scales can be prepared in a single step using strong acid and low temperature [8].

MATERIALS AND SAMPLES PREPARATION

The composite samples under investigation will be prepared using the hydrothermal heating method, which relies on a solution-based reaction approach [9]. Hydrothermal processes have many advantages, including the ability to synthesise nanoparticles over a wide temperature range, from room temperature to high temperatures [10]. To control the morphological structure, either lower or higher pressures can be applied to the reactor, depending on the vapour pressures within the reactor. This process can produce nanomaterials that lack stability at elevated temperatures, while minimising the loss of raw materials during the reaction [11]. For each sample, we poured 25cc of nitric acid with 25cc of deionised water into a beaker to dilute the nitric acid to 8M, after which we added 2.5cc of TTIP (Titanium Tetra Iso-Propoxide), inside the beaker and stirred the mixture by magnetic stirrer which is designed for mixing fluids of different viscosity with the help of a stirring rod that rotates very fast [12] for 15 minutes to dissolve the TTIP completely, after that we poured this mixture inside the Teflon of 150 cc volume and put it in the autoclave, after that the autoclave was tightly closed and then transferred to the oven: For sample 1, the temperature was set at 140°C, for sample 2 at 180°C and for sample 3 at 220°C, all samples were left in the oven for 8 hours, and after that the oven was turned off and each sample was left to cool down (get cold) to room temperature, then we opened the autoclave and after that we washed the product with deionised water for several times to remove the impurities from the main product. Thin films were formed on a glass base using a spin coater.

CHARACTERIZATION

X- Ray Characterization

The crystal structure and lattice parameters were first characterised using XRD (X-ray diffractometer), which has the following characteristics: Axis type of scan (Gonio), start position = (20°), end position $2\theta = (79.9900^\circ)$, step size $2\theta = (0.0500)$, scan step time = (1.) s, scan type: preset time, goniometer radius (240mm), measurement temperature = (25°C), anode material is Cu, K-Alpha, wavelength $\lambda = (1.54060 \text{ \AA})$.

FESEM and UV-V Characterization

Field Emission Electronic Microscopy (FESEMi-NovalNano sem), operating voltage magnitude (18 K.V) was used to obtain information about the morphology of the surface. Optical properties are a measure of a substance's interaction with light and include refraction index, reflection, absorption, polarisation and transmission. Since light is electromagnetic waves, most optical phenomena can be calculated using the classical electromagnetic description of light [13]. The absorption and transmittance spectra ultra violet-visible were calculated using (Shimadzu-Japan's, model 1800.0) calculation wavelength was in the range (190. to 1100.) nm, to characterize these optical properties of TiO₂ nanoparticles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) 1

Based on the results of the X-ray diffraction study and comparing them with the other practical results of other previous studies, it is important to know that the importance of X-ray studies lies in understanding the crystalline structure of the substance, as well as understanding the material phases, the nature of atomic arrangements in crystalline planes and their directions[14]. It should be noted that unique diffraction peaks occur at the planes shown in the image below Figure 1. It should be noted that the X-ray diffraction patterns of the first sample and the other samples are identical, which is only natural given that none of the prohibiting factors - temperature or ethylene glycol concentration - can alter the basic composition of a substance for a single compound. We observe that all the prohibited samples have characteristic peaks as shown in Figure 1, which are (110) at $2\theta = 27.48^\circ$ and (020) at $2\theta = 39.22^\circ$, (120) at $2\theta = 44.15^\circ$, (121) at $2\theta = 53$, (220) at $2\theta = 56$, and (112) at $2\theta = 69$ (the angle is in degrees) with the rutile phase. The results of the X-ray diffraction showed that the samples blocked with different concentrations of nitric acid HNO₃ and tetraisopropoxide TTIP are a mixture of anatase and rutile phases and have a tetragonal crystal structure. The lattice spacing d_{hkl} was calculated using Bragg's law $[2d \sin \theta = n\lambda]$ [15] and is approximately $3.24 \sim 1.24 \text{ \AA}$, which is shown in the table along with the number of values obtained from the diffraction pattern. Lattice constants was calculated for all samples (140, 180, 220) °C which are $a = b = 3784 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9515 \text{ \AA}$ by using $[\frac{1}{d^2} = (h^2 + k^2)/(a^2 + b^2) + l^2/c^2]$ for tetragonal structure, these findings are consistent with these studies [16-17].

Figure1. X-Ray Diffraction Pattern for 140 °C, 180 °C and 220 °C Samples

FESEM Analysis

Figure 2 shows FESEM images of TiO₂ nanostructure, where temperature and time has a major effect on shape and grain size, which control most of the properties of the composite, for example energy band gap E_g it can be affected by grain size, where the smaller the crystal size, the larger the energy gap, resulting in absorption of light at shorter wavelengths (higher energies) due to quantum confinement, especially with semiconductors. As for scattering, larger crystals result in less scattering of light, making the material more transparent; smaller crystals, especially in nanomaterials, increase scattering of light, which can cause the material to darken or change colour; as for optical absorption, it decreases at longer wavelengths in materials with small crystal sizes, while it increases at shorter wavelengths due to the increase in energy gap. If we notice Figure.2.a

which represent Sample1 prepared at 140 °C, it has a large semispherical grains around 117.298 ~ 148.355 nm and a little of pores that show a smooth surface. Figure.2b can show the picture of the surface for sample 2 prepared at 180 °C, it have a crystalline grain size about 85 ~ 124.981 nm and that smaller than the size of sample1, and with a little of pores that indicate a smooth nature of the surface. In this work as the temperature increase the grain size decrease as a result and if we look at the feSEM picture of sample3 we will find the size of crystal grains is decreasing about 56.545 ~ 89.056 nm, like a small balls in shape and smaller than other two samples and have a very tiny pores. The decrease in grain size with increasing temperature is often due to the increase in nucleation rate, the appearance of crystal defects or the change in crystal growth mechanism when a certain temperature is exceeded. Achieving a balance between temperature and cooling rate can help to control grain size and this study is similar to [18].

Figure 2. FESEM Images: a-sample1, b-sample2, c- sample3.

Optical Properties Analysis 3

Absorption, transmission, reflection and refractive index are examples of optical properties that confirm how a substance interacts with light. When a semiconductor absorbs photons with energy equal to or greater than its band gap, an electron moves from the valence band (VB) to the conduction band (CB), resulting in an increase in electrical conductivity. Figure 3.a shows the UV-vis transmittance spectra for sample 1, which has a low transmittance of about 17% at a short wavelength of 384 nm, which is in the ultraviolet region with high electronic absorption due to electronic transitions. The transmittance then gradually increases to 55% at 1000 nm in the infrared region.

Figure 3-b shows the transmittance of sample 2, which shows a gradient from 11.5% at 200 nm to 6.5% at 550 nm, as indicated by the curve. This indicates a minimum transmittance in the visible spectrum (red light region), confirming the presence of impurities within the structure of this sample. Figure 3-c shows the transmittance ratio for sample 3, which has a transmittance of 13% in the UV region at 379 nm. The low transmittance in this region is due to high electronic absorption, which is inversely related to transmittance. The decreasing transmittance ratio continues in the infrared region and this decrease in transmittance may be due to vibrations of chemical bonds as mentioned in [19].

Figure 4-a shows that the absorbance of sample #1, which peaked at 0.67% at 200nm wavelength, after that it starts to increase up to 0.8% which is the maximum value at the 400nm edge, after this point the absorbance starts to decrease as λ decreases in the visible light spectrum. In general, this level of absorbance is suitable for transparent materials. As the relationship between transparency and absorbance is not linear, but it is exponential relationship, so we can notice this agree with Figure4-b for sample 2, which shows transmittance percentage according to λ change, starting from 0.95% at 200nm and then immediately increased up to 1.20% when λ is 500nm. Almost

sample 3 Figure4-c have a similar absorbance to that prepared at 180°C, and this absorbance had increased from 0.9 to 1.2% at the 400nm edge. This small increase in absorbance with sample 2 and 3 may be due to the increase in energy band gap, or other cause may be some defects in the crystals contribute to the increase in absorbance ratio. As for the first structure prepared at 140°C, we can attribute the low absorbance to the high purity of the structure and smaller Eg value, if this analysis agrees with the work[20].

Figure 3. UV-Vis Transmittance Spectra: a-sample1 ,b-sample2, c-sample3

Figure 4. UV-Vis Absorbance Spectra of: a-sample1, b-sample2, c-sample3

Band gap energy Eg

The optical behaviour of the substance also depends on the incident photon energy according to the equation: $[(\alpha h\nu) = A(h\nu - E_g)^{1/n}]$ [20]. In this work we used the Tauc approach to determine the value of Eg by plotting the photon energy against the number of photons and determining the value of Eg by applying the extrapolation principle to the curve. For structure1 the band gap was (2.62 eV) and structure2 (2.82 eV) also sample3 has a wider band gap around 2.86eV, where this gradual increase in band gap energy with increasing temperature can be explained as follows: the decreasing crystal size leads to quantization of energy levels, reduced overlap between orbitals and increased surface effects leading to an increase in the energy gap and these results agree with study [21].

Figure 5. Calculated E_g from the Relation of $(\alpha hv)^2$ Versus (hv) by Applying Extrapolation Principle for a-(140°C), b-(180°C), c-(220°C)

CONCLUSIONS

The preparation temperature did not affect the structural properties of the three samples, where the lattice constants and crystal planes remained almost unchanged. Regular heating to (140, 180, 220)°C resulted in a decrease in crystal size and caused a larger band gap, which led to a decrease in electrical conductivity. Increasing the preparation temperature of TiO₂ nanoparticles gives a higher transmittance, but impurities play an important role in decreasing the transmittance.

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